

Minutes of the 52nd Experimenters' Meeting

The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Tuesday 26th November 2013

(This document was finalised on 17th April 2014)

Present:

Dr Bogdan Antonescu ⁷	(BA)	
Dr Joelle Buxmann ⁴	(JB)	
Dr Helen Clark ³	(HC)	
Mr Les Dean ^{1,5}	(LD)	
Dr Jon Eastment ^{5,6}	(JDE)	
Mr David Edwards ⁴	(DE)	
Dr Catherine Gaffard ⁴	(CG)	
Dr David Hooper ^{5,6}	(DAH)	Secretary
Dr Chris Lee ⁸	(CFL)	
Dr Emily Norton ⁷	(EGN)	
Dr Graham Parton ^{2,6}	(GAP)	
Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁷	(HMAR)	
Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁷	(GV)	Chair

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP)	Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
COPE	CONvective Precipitation Experiment
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FGAM	Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
GPS	Global Positioning System
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PC	Personal Computer
PCA	BLWP's data acquisition computer
PCT	BLWP's processing computer
PV	Potential Vorticity
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 51st meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he was in the process of setting up the archive.

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made good progress on 51.6.1 and would give details in section 6a. Items 47.2.1 and 47.2.2 will not be carried out until 51.6.1 has been completed.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

This remains a low priority task.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.2 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

ONGOING

LD reported that he is continuing to improve his understanding of the transmitters. Although he thought that it would be possible to return the spare transmitter to working order, this could not be achieved in the limited time available through the contract for local technical support.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.1 GAP to create a link from the Cardington dataset webpage on the BADC to the FGAM wind-profiler page.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 50.5.1 EGN to liaise with GAP in order to sort out the archiving of BLWP data on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that work on the second item is in progress.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had investigated the current options and that he would give details in section 4b.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that DE had sent him some data, but that he (DAH) had not yet had time to do anything further.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Miscellaneous issues

NERC's atmospheric radar facilities - i.e. the MSTRF, the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), and EISCAT support - will transfer from its Services and Facilities (S&F) portfolio to the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) in April 2014. The full implications of this move are not yet clear. Owing to their operational reliance of the MSTR's wind profile data, the Met Office have already expressed concern about the uncertainty in future funding. Stephen Mobbs has consequently written them a letter pledging NCAS's continued support for the MSTRF in the medium term.

NERC has a new logo. It is available in two formats and in two colour combinations. The black-and-white versions will be adopted for the MSTRF (see first page of these minutes) since the olive-and-green versions clash badly with the existing colour scheme.

GV has been contacted by two TV production teams (one from the BBC and one from Channel 4), who are looking for interesting atmosphere/weather stories and filming locations. They have subsequently been in touch with both the MSTRF and Chilbolton. GV pointed out that Felicity Perry, NCAS's Communications Manager, should be kept informed of any interactions with the media.

DAH will be giving an Institute of Physics lecture on Noctilucent Clouds at Aberystwyth University on 5th December 2013.

3b) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units have indicated brief (~ 1 s) electricity supply disruptions on 2 occasions during the past six months: on 31st July 2013, and on 28th September. A 20 s disruption at 06:21 UT on 28th September appears to have triggered the failure of the sky-camera's power supply - see section 4e. A 9 minute disruption (13:14 - 13:23 UT) on 2nd November 2013 led to gaps in the WXT510 and LD40 data streams. This made it clear that the instruments had not been powered through UPS units. This situation has now been rectified.

3c) Telecommunications

The MSTRF's supplementary website - <http://www.mstrf.eclipse.co.uk> - was not being updated from 20:20 UT on 4th July 2013 until 08:10 UT the following morning. Although DAH had initially assumed that the broadband router had lost its connection, the problem was caused by the Internet Service Provider (ISP) carrying out maintenance on their ftp server.

The broadband router lost its connection on 5 occasions: shortly after 21:51 UT on Sunday 14th July 2013, around 22:51 UT on Thursday 19th September, around 00:51 on Sunday 13th October and again

shortly after 11:51 UT, and around 00:51 UT on Saturday 16th November. In all cases, the connection was re-established by power-cycling the router using the text-message-activated relay unit. This typically resulted in 10 hours downtime before the problem was spotted the following morning. Approximately 4 hours of lost connection on the afternoon of Wednesday 16th October 2013 turned out to be the result of a problem at a telephone exchange in the Birmingham area.

DE suggested that the Met Office could set up an automatic e-mail alert system to indicate when Aberystwyth wind-profile data had failed to arrive on time. However, DAH pointed out that the broadband connection was typically lost late at night and re-established first thing the following morning. Consequently an e-mail alert would not lead to reduced downtime. GV recommended that someone else within RAL should have the responsibility for checking on the connection during periods when DAH is on leave.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

No rain was detected by the tipping bucket raingauge between 6th and 12th September 2013. The WXT510 detected rain on each of these days. The problem was the result of LD accidentally reassembled the unit with the inlet pointing in the wrong direction after he cleaned it on the morning of the 6th. Rain was detected again on the 13th after LD had rectified the problem.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

With regards to action item 51.4.1, DAH has established that he will need to make a number of co-ordinated changes in order to increase the local storage capacity at Frongoch. He will have to install a new logger, write a new acquisition script, and use a new data download program. Consequently, he will need to simultaneously make equivalent changes to the surface met sensor acquisition system. He plans to implement these changes when the current data acquisition PC is replaced. The current one is running Windows XP, which will cease to be supported by Microsoft in early 2014.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There is a known bug in the software that is used to create the daily WXT510 netCDF files for the BADC. The software crashes whenever there is a gap in the raw data. Consequently no files have been uploaded to the BADC for 19th, 20th and 23rd September 2013, and for 3rd and 5th October 2013. It will be possible to create the netCDF files once the bug has been fixed.

The WXT510 failed to detect the rain seen by the tipping bucket raingauge on 8th October 2013. It succeeded in detecting the rain of the following day without any intervention having been taken.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There was an 11 minute gap in data acquisition (11:31 - 11:42) UT on 5th November 2013 whilst LD transferred the instrument onto a UPS unit - see section 3b. Previously, there had been a 9 minute gap (13:14 - 13:23 UT) on 2nd November 2013 as the result of an electricity supply disruption.

4e) Sky-camera

This instrument stopped functioning at the time of a 20 s electricity supply disruption on 28th September 2013 - see section 3b. It seems likely that its power supply has failed. However, since the camera is approximately 4 m above the ground and there is no ladder at site capable of reaching it, it remains out of action.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

The 2013 season was a good one for NLC observers in the northern British Isles. However, it was not so good for southern England, largely owing to tropospheric cloud cover. The NLC camera at Chilbolton (51.1°N) only observed NLCs on 4 occasions (all in the dawn): on 3rd, 10th, and 14th June, and on 15th July 2013. Observations will be resumed in late May 2014.

4g) MST Radar

DE presented details of the MST Radar's data quality over the past six months. The EUCOS (EUMETNET Composite Observing System) statistics are based (since October 2012) on comparisons with the ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) model, which has a relatively coarse horizontal grid separation of 12 km. The Met Office statistics are based on comparisons with their own UKV model, which has a 1.5 km grid separation. DE noticed, from the EUCOS statistics, a small step increase in early May 2013 in the daily number of observations that were delivered on time. He suspects that this might be the result of changes to the time window within which observations are regarded as being on time. The mean vector differences only exceeded the 5 m s^{-1} target maximum on 3 occasions and otherwise indicated consistently good data quality. The wind directions showed more variability. However, as GV pointed out, this has reduced significance when the wind speed is low, as it was during June and July 2013.

The Met Office's statistics consistently show a slight positive bias in radar wind speed in the troposphere and a slight negative bias in the stratosphere. Nevertheless, the observed and model values tend to be within 1 m s^{-1} of each other. Even the root mean square (RMS) differences tend to be no more than 3 or 4 m s^{-1} . The Met Office are happy with this level of consistency. Larger differences tend to be confined to the winter months and are associated with the jet stream. This is consistent with what is seen in model fields. DE has found that the standard deviation of the observed winds is closely correlated with the average wind speed. At stratospheric altitudes the standard deviation is slightly smaller than for the equivalent speed at tropospheric altitudes.

DAH then presented details of specific issues encountered by the radar over the past six months. The transmitter powering antenna sector B has frequently been out of action: 8 times in July 2013, 4 times in August, 2 times in September, and 3 times in October. This has mostly been the result of a blown fuse, but there were occasional analogue errors. The transmitter powering antenna sector C was out of action on 4 occasions. During one of these, between 27th and 30th July 2013, the transmitter was restarted several times, but typically blew its fuse within 30 minutes. The transmitters for sectors B and C both blew their fuses on the morning of 1st August 2013 and were repaired on the following day.

The radar suffered from interference on 4 occasions, none of which lasted for more than 5 hours. It appeared to be suffering from interference between 12th and 15th November 2013. However, the reduced coverage turned out to be the result of a raised noise floor. This used to be seen whenever the transmitter for sector A shut down with an analogue error. LD had to switch out each antenna sector in turn before discovering that the problem was related to the receiver feed from sector E. This feed remains disconnected until LD can find the underlying cause of the problem.

There have been a few minor issue with beam steering modules. Mostly there have been one-off reports of unusual behaviour. No action was taken in these cases. The unit for quad number 30 was replaced on 30th July 2013 after its operations became intermittent. The unit for quad number 67 was replaced on 22nd October 2013 after it indicated high VSWR (voltage standing wave ratio) values.

The output power setting was raised from level 4 to 5 on the transmitter for antenna sector E on 28th June 2013. The same was done for the transmitters in sectors A and C on 2nd July 2013.

LD commented on the fact that although the Facility has spare units for most of the radar system, there

is no spare radar-control/pre-processor unit. He thought that effort should be put into making a backup system.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) instruments

The Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements (FGAM) is being renamed as the Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF). The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) will be known officially as the NCAS Mobile Radar Wind Profiler. This will distinguish it from the new mobile X-band radar.

EGN reported that the BLWP is currently at Cardington. During the summer of 2013 it was operated successfully at Davidstow in Cornwall in support of the CONvective Precipitation Experiment (COPE). However, it would intermittently stop working and had to be restarted manually. Despite an extensive investigation, no hardware cause for the problem could be found. The problem disappeared when the software was rolled back to the November 2012 version, which calculates spectra on a processing board rather than on the acquisition computer, PCA. The power supply unit failed after COPE and had to be sent back to Degreane for repairs. Philipp Currier (from Degreane) came to Cardington in November 2013 in order to carry out the yearly maintenance on the BLWP. He installed a debugged version of the latest software (version 5.43). This once again allows spectra to be calculated on PCA. It also allows the site information to be updated without modifying the "harpar.dat" file. If the software detects a signal at high altitudes, it can automatically adjust the inter-pulse period for the low mode to avoid range aliasing.

There have also been some changes to the processing computer, PCT. It is better able to deal with intermittent precipitation and now rejects fewer data points. Isolated wind barbs have to pass quality control checks rather than being automatically accepted. Turbulence data products can now be displayed and retrieved from the ".trw" binary files. Boundary layer height and bright band detection algorithms are under development. IDL code has been adapted to cope with the latest-format Degreane files. Data products are now being archived on the BADC in netCDF files.

HMAR reported on the Elight lidar. He has been trying to update the complex Labview software, which has been a time consuming task. He has successfully managed to implement photon counting, which should increase height coverage. He is hoping to add water vapour and N₂ Raman channels to the system.

GV reported that the Leosphere lidar is not currently working. However, the static lidar system is working well. A new staff member at Manchester is updating the software. It is hoped that this will allow a rapid response in case of future volcanic ash episodes. GV had stated at the previous meeting that the lidar had detected ash from a volcano in Alaska. In fact, it turned out that it had detected particles from biomass burning in Canada. There was one layer at an altitude of approximately 3 km and a second one at 8 km. The Aberystwyth lidar was the only one to see the upper layer. The new Met Office lidars should be able to detect such a layer.

5b) Other Guest Instruments - DAH

During the latter part of 2013, two air sampling instruments were operated at the radar site. The one from Aberystwyth University trapped air samples into containers, which were then returned to the lab for analysis. The one from the University of Manchester sampled the air in situ. The central aim of the project was to study the role of biological particles (such as spores, pollen, and bacterial cells) as cloud condensation nuclei.

There is nothing to report on the Met Office's GPS receiver or on the lightning detector.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) How representative are single-cycle MST Radar winds? - DAH

This investigation was prompted by DE's discovery of sporadic occurrences of rogue (i.e. clearly-unrealistic) winds in the Met Office's MST radar data stream. The source of the problem turned out to be the factor used to compensate wind speeds for the differences between the nominal and effective zenith angles of the radar beams (CFL also considers this factor in Section 6b below). It became apparent that this factor varies significantly from cycle to cycle. Consequently it is adding noise to the single cycle estimates of the wind vector even when it is not generating rogue winds. However, further investigation has shown that this is neither the only nor the largest contribution to cycle to cycle wind variability, which can be as large as $\pm 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for wind speeds of around 50 m s^{-1} .

DAH emphasised the need to apply smoothing in time in order to obtain a more-representative estimate of the background wind. He has investigated the effects of different levels of smoothing by considering the magnitude of the wind vector difference evaluated over the same time interval. The latter represents a combination of the random measurement error and the natural variability of the wind. As might be expected, the principal effect of low levels of smoothing is to reduce the former. However, the latter begins to dominate at longer time scales. Smoothing over 3 or 4 cycles (which have a typical separation of 5 minutes 14 seconds) is not quite sufficient, but somewhere between 5 and 7 cycles appears to be optimal. The 30 minute averaging used for the Met Office's data stream corresponds to approximately 6 cycles.

DAH found a few examples of the horizontal wind speed apparently being modulated by mountain wave activity over time scales of more than an hour. He was unsure whether this was a real effect or an artefact of the vertical velocity contaminating the horizontal wind component. There is a particularly clear case on 6th February 2013, when peak to peak amplitudes of up to 15 m s^{-1} can be seen at altitudes of between 10 and 15 km. However, there is no fixed phase relationship between the vertical and horizontal wind perturbations. GV suggested that the horizontal wind perturbations could be real since the Egrett aircraft had detected similar patterns during a campaign conducted in 2000.

6b) MST winds and vertical velocities - CFL

Since 2009, nearly 130 radiosondes have been launched from the MST radar site during a variety of campaigns. CFL has been using the data to evaluate the accuracy of MST radar winds. There has been a clear improvement as a result of the 2011 renovation. Afterwards, there is a close agreement between the vertical velocities derived directly from the vertical beam radial velocities and those derived indirectly from combining the complementary off-vertical beam (i.e. those that are separated by 180° in azimuth) radial velocities. Prior to the renovation, the agreement was not so good and showed a dependence on the horizontal wind speed.

There is also a better agreement between the radar and radiosonde wind speeds post-renovation. However, the radar speeds still show a slight positive bias at tropospheric altitudes and a slight negative bias at lower-stratospheric altitudes - c.f. model comparison statistics in section 4g. The shape of this profile closely matches that of the mean vertical velocity, suggesting that mountain waves might be responsible for the differences. Since radiosondes drift horizontally as they rise, they will sample different phases of any mountain waves present compared to the radar.

CFL has also examined the role of the radar wind speed compensation factor (described by DAH in section 6a) for the accuracy of radar-derived winds. It is clear that there is a better statistical fit between the radar and radiosonde winds when this factor is applied. However, the current method of calculating it assumes that there is no azimuthal anisotropy of radar return signal power. CFL used data from the immediate post-renovation period, when observations were made using all 17 available beam pointing directions, to test this. Averaged over 8 weeks of observations, there was only one altitude region (around 7.5 km) where there was a noticeable azimuthal anisotropy. CFL also showed that, from a

statistical point of view, the match between radar and radiosondes was equally good if climatological values of the wind speed compensation factor were used or if they were calculated dynamically.

6c) Should all BLWP data be reprocessed with the latest version of the Degreane software? - EGN

EGN has reprocessed observations made during the 2002 NAMBLEX campaign using the latest version of the Degreane software. Overall, the original and reprocessed data look quite similar. However, the latest software blanks the winds from the lowest altitudes, which were always considered to be a bit unreliable. It also appears to be occasionally blanking winds that appeared to have been reliable. It has been necessary to fine-tune some of the processing parameters so that rainfall and the passage of fronts are not obscured in this way.

6d) Sunphotometers for the CAA lidar network - JB

The purpose of the network is to help the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) make better-informed decisions in the event of volcanic ash affecting British airspace. It will consist of a lidar and a sunphotometer being operated in tandem at nine fixed sites and on one mobile platform. The data will be fed into the Met Office's existing LIDARNET, which is used for the laser ceilometers.

The Cimel CE318 sunphotometers will mainly be used in sun-tracking mode, which provides the aerosol optical depth and the water vapour column. They can alternatively be operated at a fixed zenith angle and scanned in azimuth or at a fixed azimuth and scanned in zenith angle. This allows the aerosol size distribution to be determined. As part of the acceptance testing, a Cimel sunphotometer has been operated alongside a Middleton instrument. The correlation between the two sets of measurements was generally good. There was also a good correlation between the water vapour columns derived from the Cimel sunphotometer and from GPS measurements. The Met Office would like to integrate the measurements from the new instruments into the international AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK (AERONET). Amongst other things, this will provide a reference for data quality assessment. The acceptance testing of the sunphotometers will be completed by the beginning of 2014.

6e) Organised convection ahead of a PV anomaly - BA

This TROSIAD case study, from 16th September 2011, corresponds to Intensive Observation Period (IOP) 1 of the DIAMET (DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms) campaign. A FAAM (Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements) flight deployed dropsondes as it flew across southern Ireland. The dominant feature at the 500 hPa level was a trough, which was located to the west of Ireland at 00 UT. During the next 12 hours it became elongated along an approximately south-east/north-west axis. The rainfall radar images show isolated convective cells being initiated over Ireland at 03 UT. During the next few hours these merged into a distinct band of precipitation, which moved eastward.

The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) mesoscale model reproduces the features of this day quite well (although it puts the precipitation band slightly to the west of where it was observed). This shows that its output is suitable for analysing the mesoscale situation in more detail. The map of equivalent potential temperature (θ_e) at the surface shows a band of relatively moist air moving northwards and eastwards over Ireland during the course of the morning. Enhanced values of Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE) are found within this band. However, the convective activity also depends on the presence of an upper level Potential Vorticity (PV) anomaly and on frontogenesis taking place. Frontogenesis can no longer provide a trigger mechanism by 12 UT. BA thinks that orographic enhancement might provide the trigger mechanism at 12 UT, when the precipitation band has moved under the tropopause fold and therefore entered a region of relative stability.

6f) Multibanded structure of tropopause folds - HMAR

This is a side project that HMAR has been working on with BA. Tropopause folds show up clearly in MST radar observations owing to the enhanced signal power and enhanced wind shear. They also show

up clearly in radiosonde data as dry, statically stable layers. This project has additionally considered data from approximately 400 ozonesondes that were launched from Aberystwyth during the 1990s. In several cases, the folds were characterised by two rather than one peak in ozone concentration. GV pointed out that folds are commonly associated with north-westerly flows. Stratospheric air can descend through the fold for several thousand kilometres upstream. These features can remain distinct for long periods of time, in one case persisting for 11 days after the fold first appeared.

7. Any Other Business

GV will be away on a campaign during January and February 2014. The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for June 2014.